

The Mythic in the Legendary, and Vice Versa: A Theoretical-Analytical Appraisal of the Kumauni Legend of Haru Singh Heet

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Abstract

Since the subject of the study in the paper is a mythic legend, it delves – to begin with – just deep enough into the discipline of folklore to delineate its range and thematic contours. Having done that, and having also attempted to define folklore and its functions, the paper goes on to briefly discuss and define legend as a subgenre of folklore. In order to do so, the paper refers to and cites from the authentic works of well-established scholars in the field of folklore studies. The purpose of this part of the paper is to lay the general theoretical groundwork on which to build the analysis of the legend that follows in the second part.

In the second part, the paper takes up for an analytical appraisal and contextual interpretation the Kumauni legend of Haru Singh Heet which originated not earlier than, roughly, some 200 years ago. The time of the origin of the legend is located at an interesting juncture in the history of Kumaun when the region was a part of the Gorkhali Empire that had its imperial seat in Kathmandu. The paper makes a close study and analysis of the text of the mythic legend as recorded by Kheemanand Sharma and published in 1975. The analysis follows the chronology of the tale from the opening of the narration to the end. The idea behind this method of analysis is to bring out and critically comment on the happenings and events in the legend that track a familiar pattern of the arrival of a folk-hero on scene, his growth and development in the relevant senses of the words, and his epic journey to and from his prize and/or goal. As it happens in some popular myths and legends of the world, the hero of the legend under study in the paper dies, too, but earns an eternity in and through the ritualistic singing and ceremonial performance of the tale at some local events like ‘Jagar’.

Introduction

Myths and legends, along with fables, folk dances, folk drama, folk songs etcetera are all genres of folklore; and folklore, in general, has its history closely intertwined with the development of human society and culture over several thousand years. However, Folkloristics or Folklore Studies as an academic discipline can only be seen starting sometime around the middle of the 19th Century. The term ‘folklore’, originally spelt with a hyphen as ‘folk-lore’, is said to have been suggested by “Mr. Thoms, in 1846, to designate ‘that department of the study of

antiquities and archaeology which embraces everything relating to ancient observances and customs, to the notions, beliefs, traditions, superstitions, and prejudices of the common people.” (Cox 03). There, cited by Cox in his book published in 1895, we have arguably the first ever definition of folklore by William John Thoms. More than 150 years later, in our own 21st Century (almost a quarter of which is in the past already), when Folklore Studies are an established and thriving field of study and research, the definition of folklore has only grown wider to cover almost all areas of life: “The study of folklore touches upon every dimension of human experience and artistic expression. It has grown out of the study of literature, has roots in anthropology, and contains elements of psychology and sociology. In many ways, it is the study of culture...” (Sims & Stephens 03). That is quite a broad definition and reveals the extensive multidisciplinary scope of folklore studies. Yet, trying to succinctly define folklore can be a frustrating exercise because there are more than a score definitions of it. Mariah Leach’s *Standard Dictionary of Folklore, Mythology and Legend*, as Francis Lee Utley informs, has “twenty one definitions of folklore” (qtd. in Dundes 07). Rather than losing ourselves in the maze of those definitions, it should be a more fruitful exercise to know what goes into and gets included in folklore. And to know that, we take a long quote from Alan Dundes:

Folklore includes myths, legends, folktales, jokes, proverbs, riddles, chants, charms, blessings, curses, oaths, insults, retorts, taunts, teases, toasts, tongue-twisters, and greetings and leave-taking formulas. It also includes folk costume, folk dance, folk drama (and mime), folk art, folk belief (or superstition), folk medicine, folk instrumental music, folksongs, folk speech, folk similes, folk metaphors, and names... (03).

Once we have arrived at a reasonably open and clear understanding of folklore, we would need to know about its role. To put it simply, we would want to know what folklore does. William R. Bascom speaks of four functions of folklore. The first, as Bascom explains through a long illustrative discussion, is the function of revealing “man’s frustrations and attempts to escape in fantasy from repressions imposed upon him by society, whether these repressions be sexual or otherwise and whether they result from taboos or incest or polygamy, or from a taboo on laughing at a person afflicted by yaws” (qtd. in Dundes 290). The second function of folklore, according to Bascom, is the function of “validating culture” and “justifying its rituals and institutions to those who perform them”; the third is the function “it plays in education, particularly, but not exclusively, in non-literate societies”; and the fourth is the function of “maintaining conformity to the accepted patterns of behaviour” (qtd. in Dundes 292-294).

Legend, as has been noted earlier, is a genre of folklore. Yet, legend can be seen as developing into a prolific (sub)genre in its own right over the past centuries. Etymologically originating in the medieval Latin word *legenda*, and going into Old French as the noun *legende*, the word legend has had a long history of meanings, of which untruth and/or falsehood, too, had been one for a reckonable period of time. However, Brothers Grimm (or Grimm brothers), to whom is generally attributed the inauguration of folklore as a field of academic study, notice a certain historicity in the genre of legend. Compared to fairytale, which is “more poetic, the legend is more historical” and “it adheres always to that which we are conscious of and know well, such as a locale or a name that has been secured through history” (Grimm 01). Writing in 1990, Tangherlini largely concurs with Grimm brothers and says, “[w]hile the folktale uses reality in an ironic way, legend tries to reconstruct reality in a believable fashion” (372). Elaborating further, he adds that “[l]egend narrative is linked to outer reality, opposed to the inner reality of folktale, making specific allusions to verifiable topographic features or historical personages”, and that legends could “be used as secondary historical source” (Tangherlini 372 & 379). What he does after critically considering all aspects of the genre, with copious references to several scholarly sources, is to give us a fairly contemporary definition of legend:

Legend, typically, is a short (mono-) episodic, traditional, highly ecotypified, historicised narrative performed in a conversational mode, reflecting on a psychological level a symbolic representation of folk belief and collective experiences and serving as a reaffirmation of commonly held values of the group to whose tradition it belongs. (385)

A legend, thus, being quasi-historical in nature and bound to a geographical locale and/or to a specific person or a set of persons, has a sort of time-bound context. Yet, (as can be observed) legends live and continue to fascinate even in our era, which is said to be rational, because they earn a timeless context over time. This timelessness of legends generally grows from the timeless and universal values they espouse. There are scores of legends the world over that continue to fascinate and continue to be loved because woven intricately in them (in their warp and weft) are certain timeless values. For example, the legends of Lady Godiva, King Arthur, Robin Hood (all from England) and so many more from elsewhere in the world, particularly of indigenous origin, get their continuing charm and enduring relevance from what they seem to instruct. Individually, every legend attaches symbiotically to a locale and its people, yet it shares some universal characteristics with the legends of the rest of the world. It is so because legends, with the element of the folk being predominant in them, connect with the basic and the fundamental in human experience. Legends of heroism and of heroes doing heroic deeds

have an ostensible purpose. In some societies, such legends appear more in frequency and in a greater number. It is so because these societies need the legends of heroism; they need them in a greater number and in a greater frequency than in some other societies. For example, India, being the site of several conflicts in the past 9-10 centuries between the natives and the rulers belonging to the clans crossing over from across her north-western borders, is among those societies where heroic legends have grown in good frequency and number and have also been very popular. The reason, as Kathryn Hansen states, is that mytho-historical or legendary accounts of heroic behaviour “frame paradigms of gendered conduct that assist both women and men in defining their identities, inculcating values to the young, and judging the actions of others” (7).

Discussion

Fulfilling the requisites to fully qualify as a legend is the tale of Haru Singh Heet in the Kumaun region of what is now the hill state of Uttarakhand in north India. While popular belief locates the origin of the name of the region in a story in the *Manas Khand* of *Skand Purana* — the very well-known story of the churning of the ocean of milk, while archaeologists (by reference to the prehistoric Lakh-Udiyar cave shelter in Barechhina, Almora) speak of a long history of human habitation in the region, and while historians see a connection between the region and the ancient Central Himalayan Kuninda Kingdom from 2nd Century BCE to 3rd Century CE, what concerns this paper more is the history of the region around late 18th Century and very early 19th, in which is lodged the oral historical legend of Haru Singh. After the region had been ruled by the Katyuri dynasty, which took over the region from a branch of the splintered Kuninda dynasty, and after the Chand kings had taken over the region from the Katyuri Kings in decline and had themselves weakened by the later half of the 18th Century to lose control over the region, the Gorkhas of Nepal invaded and captured Kumaun (and Garhwal) in 1790 and annexed it to the Gorkhali Empire that had its seat in Kathmandu. The Gorkha rule in Kumaun came to an end in 1816 when they were defeated by the East India Company in the Anglo-Nepalese war.

The legend of Haru Singh comes to us from this very period in the history of Kumaun. We can treat the legend as a part of the oral history of the region, which it certainly is; and its protagonist or hero, Haru Singh, lived during the Gorkha rule in Kumaun from 1790-91 to

1815-16. His life, though short, must already have come to be preserved in the stories told and retold after his death because his was a story of bravery, justice, love and sacrifice — the timeless values that a hero, especially belonging to a ruling clan, must have, and the timeless values that the ballad this paper studies recommends and lauds directly or indirectly in many of its verses. It is easy to surmise that the elements of lore and of legend kept on entering and becoming parts of the story as it continued to grow in its oral form. The easiest to memorise and the easiest to communicate is the oral form of poetic recitation; and the tale of Haru Singh evolved in this form for around 150 years till it finally came to be scripted by Kheemanand Sharma in a ballad with end-rhyming couplets. The available text of the ballad that this paper cites throughout is a digitised version of the 12th edition of the text published by Kumauni Sahitya Sadan, Delhi, in 1975. In the short introduction, running in just half a page, Kheemanand states that his narration of Haru Singh's tale originates in the stories of the hero he had heard from his elders (02). Since another narration of the heroic poem in printed text form was either never done by any other author or is not available, we can reasonably consider Kheemanand Sharma's narration of the tale of Haru Singh Heet as the first in print.

Kheemanand begins the narration with an invocation, running in five couplets, to 'five deities'. Transcreated into English by the author of this paper, the opening couplets make the following prayer:

O Five Deities, be kind, enlighten my ignorant mind, and listen to my plea!

I pick up my pen to write, and offer my prayers to the Almighty. (09)

Instead of starting in an indefinite time (as myths generally and legends sometimes do), the ballad puts the precise date of the beginning of the chain of events right upfront:

The tale I narrate begins in seventeen hundred ninety,

When Almora and Garhwal were won over by the Gurkha mighty. (09)

It is the time, the narrator adds further, when Samar Singh, who had seven sons and seven daughters-in-law, was the absolute lord of 'Gujdu Kot, Talla Patti Sult' of Almora in Kumaun (10).

The next few couplets speak of the abundance and prosperity of Samar Singh and the territory governed by him, which was either a small kingdom or, more likely, a feudality. The autocratic power of Samar Singh, aided by his prosperity, creates pride in him and his seven brave sons start torturing people, levying unnecessary taxes, and harassing and violating young women. In a distinctly moralising tone, which runs throughout the poem, the legend attributes the

cruelties of Samar Singh and his sons to their sense turned wrong that only precedes and ensures their fall. The people who suffer the atrocities can only curse and can only pray to the Almighty to punish Samar Singh and his sons. We bring in a little of recorded history at this stage to point out that there may have been a reason for this Samar Singh and his sons in this piece of oral history to turn cruel towards their people, though the narrator telling the legend attributes this change to their pride and vanity. Mahesh Regmi, a Nepalese historian, in his book *The Imperial Gorkha* (1999), writes about the extortions and the forced labour that Kumaunis had to suffer at the hands of the Gorkhali imperial representatives and soldiers, along with, quite likely, the women of the region suffering harassment. To take a brief but sufficiently illustrative quote from the historian's book, "[n]othing has been written on how the Gorkhali rulers administered Kumaun, how they exploited its resources, and how the burden of defeat was borne by the people of Kumaun" (Regmi xv). In the light of this observation by Mahesh Regmi, it can be said that this Samar Singh of the legend started levying the extortionist taxes at the behest of the Gorkha emperor sitting far away in Kathmandu.

To proceed with the ballad, the hapless people, harassed and tortured as they are, pray and curse:

There is tyranny in Gujdu Kot, there is torture;
O God! Lend your ears to our prayer!
Take away the seven sons, make widows of their women;
They make us suffer and give us pain for no reason. (10)

Whether by divine retribution or as the effect of the curses of the people, or both, a disease spreads in the region — the disease that kills, first, Samar Singh's seven sons on seven successive days and, then, Samar Singh himself on the eighth who chokes on his sorrow (11). Subtle or explicit, moralising is one of the functions of legends, and Kheemanand's telling of the legend of Haru Singh in the ballad has enough of it wherever it fits in the narration. For instance, here is an example:

Kheemanand tells you, and you must listen;
Pride mustn't occupy your mind.
Where there is peace there is the Divine,
But pride destroys all — big or small, low or high on incline. (12)

And, so, the couplets at this stage in the ballad ascribe the destruction of Samar Singh and his sons, along with his small kingdom, to the pride that made them commit atrocities which only earned them the curses of the people.

At this stage in the ballad, the hero of the legend, Haru Singh, gets his first mention — interestingly — as a six-month-old foetus in his mother's womb. With Samar Singh and his sons gone, their kingdom dissipates and his wife and daughters-in-law fall on bad days. No one mentions the past of the family to Haru Singh as he grows up; till, perhaps, when he turns 14. As the ballad narrates it, he learns about the past of the family from another boy in a conversation after a game in which Haru Singh was playing the role of the king. Incensed, Haru Singh rushes to his mother to question her, and gets to know the truth. And then start his heroic exploits — he mounts his horse and starts on his expedition to reclaim his father's kingdom and all the dues from the fiefs in it. This is the moment of the awakening of the hero in him:

Holding a shield in one hand and a sword in the other,

Riding his mare with a saddle nice and good halter;

Thus takes off Haru to collect the taxes due for many a year. (14)

He slowly reclaims the entire kingdom that his father had ruled, and becomes the ruling prince. Having brought back happiness to the people, and having established a generous but strict rule, Haru Singh now wants to get a wife for himself. All he wants is a simple wife who would be good to his mother and his sisters-in-law (17). But, as the ways of the world go and as it happens with every successful person, he has enemies now — his sisters-in-law (the widows of his brothers) at home, and some other people outside. So, while he plans to marry someone good, his sisters-in-law go away from home, fearing that the woman Haru Singh marries would make them secondary in influence. While searching for them, he dies at the hands of his enemies; but is brought back to life by his mother's prayers to Golu Devta, the unfailing god of justice and arguably the most popular deity in the region of Kumaun. There is an instant miracle; and Haru Singh comes back to life:

The cries of the grieving mother reach Golu's ears

The deity melts, and dead Haru revives. (24)

We know already that miracles like this are usual ingredients of legends. The vital point to note here, in the context of this legend, is that Golu Devta is the principal character in another Kumauni legend of bravery and justice and sacrifice — the legend that narrates the life of Golu ji and his ascension to the status of a deity only a few centuries before Haru Singh.

Thus revived, Haru Singh finds his sisters-in-law and asks them to come back home. They do return, but scheme and contrive to send him to his death by cunningly telling him to go to the land of Bhot (the land of Bhotiyas) to marry the princess Malu Rauteli. They challenge him:

Bring Malu as your bride to us if you are a son of your mother

If not, no better than a jackal you are. (25)

The scheme of the jealous sisters-in-law is to send Haru Singh to the faraway land of the Bhotiyas to marry their princess, because they think that going to Bhot to marry Malu, the princess, would be a suicidal mission for him. It needs a mention here that Bhot was thought to be a dreaded region till a little more than half a century ago and its inhabitants, the Bhotiyas, were believed to be a community of unrelentingly ferocious people when it came to protecting their people and systems. Haru Singh's mother knows the danger and the fear of almost a certain death for her son if he goes to the land of Bhotiyas to marry Malu. She also knows about the powerful black magic the people of Bhot were and are believed to practice; and, so, she tries to dissuade Haru Singh:

Do not go to the land of Bhot, my dear son, don't!

None can win against Bhotiyas; you, too, won't (26).

Neither his mother's pleading nor the talk of dreadful black magic can stop Haru Singh; he is adamant, and starts off to get Malu Rauteli as his bride. Before leaving, however, he makes a prayer to the spirits of his ancestors for protection:

He folds hands and says his prayers,

Do not abandon me, my godly ancestors.

Spurred by my sisters-in-law, I am going on the mission,

My forefathers, ensure that I come back safe and fine. (28)

It is a longstanding belief in many cultures of the world that the spirits of ancestors are powerful protectors against unforeseen dangers; and Haru Singh's prayer to his ancestors conforms with and endorses that belief. It is also believed that the spirits can withdraw protection and even inflict harm if not prayed to and propitiated properly. In the hills of Kumaun, therefore, there is a custom in families and clans to organise rituals annually to propitiate the spirits of the ancestors.

After a long and arduous journey, Haru Singh reaches the land of Bhotiyas. The ballad narrates the dramatic first meeting of Haru Singh and Malu in a temple of Goddess, where Haru Singh goes to worship and to seek the blessings of the deity for success in his mission and for protection in this faraway land. Tired and with nowhere else to go, Haru Singh falls asleep in the temple premises. The next morning, Malu reaches the same temple, which she is wont to visit everyday to pray to Goddess for a good and brave husband. Haru Singh, now awake, sees her coming out of the temple and is charmed by her beauty, as she is charmed by his handsomeness. Thus charmed, both of them faint for a while; and when they wake up, they are in love with each other, as if their meeting and falling in love was predestined. There is little

of coincidence in their meeting and in their falling in an unshakable love instantly. While Haru Singh has travelled this distance and has prayed at the temple of Goddess for success in his mission to win and marry Malu, and while Malu, in her turn, has prayed to Goddess at this temple for years asking for a good and brave husband, their meeting at this very temple appears entirely designed, so to say, by Goddess. If Haru Singh had wanted, he could have gone back taking Malu with him; Malu even suggests so. He, however, finds it unheroic and cowardly to run away with her like this; and he doesn't want to be called and known as a thief or an abductor. So, the ballad next notes that Malu employs her magic and makes Haru Singh a fly, puts him in a small box and takes him home while his horse, made into a bumblebee, follows. While outside, Malu keeps him as a fly, and within her quarters she lets him be the man he is. The ballad then sings of Haru Singh's clandestine stay at Malu's place in Bhot, his getting killed by the fatal black magic of Gangala who buries him in Malu's garden, his being dug up and brought back to life by Malu after she gets to know, in a dream, about his death and the location of the grave.

The tale suddenly precipitates at this stage, which is the stage of Haru Singh's return to life from death. A guard overhears the sound of a conversation between Malu and Haru Singh behind closed doors and informs Malu's father, Kalu Sauk, about a stranger hiding in his daughter's quarters. As can be expected, a fight follows between Kalu Sauk's small army on the one hand and Haru Singh alone on the other. This could be a crucial situation of dilemma for Malu Rauteli, because she has to pick her side; she wouldn't stand like a spectator. And she chooses her side without even a minute's hesitation. Her guiding principle is her Dharma as a wife, which can loosely be translated as a flexible code of duties. Obviously, the code — a moral code or 'Dharma' — may not be compatible with contemporary social ethics; but, we need to bear in mind that the legend comes to us from a time more than two centuries ago and delineates the social conventions and codes of that time. And, so, Malu knows and speaks openly and boldly about her loyalty and duty, first and foremost, to her husband:

You pick up your sword and fall on them quick,
While I with all my might will weave my magic;
Do not fear, my lord, and fight bravely
While I am by your side with my duty wifely (40).

This is not a fight with weapons alone. This is also a fight with and by magic — a form of the supernatural, being invoked and employed on both the sides.

Bhotiyas throw at Haru Singh their spells powerful,
But Malu's protective magic makes them all dull and null. (40)

The twosome team of Haru Singh and Malu Rauteli wins the battle, killing almost all of the latter's kinsmen. The surviving among them beg Haru Singh to marry Malu and take her away with him. The two, then, take horses and goats, load them with as much treasure as is possible to carry, and leave.

All goes fine and happy as they travel back, making their stops at holy places for prayers, the most noteworthy among them being Bagnath and Golu Devta, also known rather affectionately as 'Goriya'. They make their prayers and offer generous tributes and offerings to the deities. After Haru Singh's victorious return home, all goes fine for some time; and then start the machinations of the seven jealous sisters-in-law. Malu is deceptively killed by them; and Haru Singh is so much grief-stricken that he decides to die. But he also knows that he, being the last living son of her mother, must perform her last rites so that her soul gets a peaceful transmigration. So, he requests his mother to die so that he can die himself without worrying about his mother. It is strange and unusual, but the mother does understand and dies. Haru Singh performs her last rites, and then, with Malu's dead body in his lap, cremates himself alive:

Holding Malu's body in his lap, Haru burns himself in fire
Oh Rama! Oh Siva! All is lost; nothing now to aspire. (47)

Conclusion

To end, the ballad blesses Haru Singh for being a justice loving brave young man. He lives in another form now — the form of a deity in temples. A deity now and, therefore, beyond death, Haru Singh listens to the appeals of victims of injustice. Disappointed elsewhere, people go to his temples to pray; and, as the ballad further notes, their prayers are heard. Living in the form of a godly spirit, Haru Singh imparts justice as a fair ruler should. In the entire narration, the ballad highlights and celebrates certain values that are both topical and timeless. Meant primarily for rulers or the people in power to observe, these values are the values of generosity, charity, and justice. The ballad foregrounds its moral purpose and doesn't mince words in deriding the vices like pride and loss of good sense. That way, it serves a moral purpose, which is one of the basic and crucial functions of folklore.

The legend of Haru Singh as narrated in a ballad form by Kheemanand, which this paper has cited throughout, spells its messages and weaves the explicitly stated morals seamlessly within the narration. The ballad carries an unmistakable element of the mythic in it. There are two occasions in the ballad when Haru Singh comes back to life after death: in the first case as a result of his mother's prayers to Golu Devta and in the second as a result of some ritual of the occult by Malu Rauteli. These two instances of the return of Haru Singh from death — his two resurrections — narrated in the ballad are decidedly the instances of the mythic, because, as Karen Armstrong explains by reference to the myths of the graves of the Neanderthals, the first of the "five important things about myth" is the fact that "it is nearly always rooted in the experience of death and the fear of extinction" (3). Thus, while this travel between the zones of life and death is a matter belonging to the domain of the mythic, the role of deities, of gods, and of the occult in the ballad is, also, decidedly mythic in nature. The role of Golu Devta, though mentioned indirectly and briefly, is vital. It is just around the beginning of his heroic career that Haru Singh is killed. If Golu Devta hadn't heard this mother's prayers and brought him back to life, Haru Singh wouldn't have gone on to become the legendary hero that he becomes in the course of time. Like the first, his second return to life, by Malu's magic, is crucial, too, because he has to get back to his own small kingdom or vassal state to prove and establish his status as a hero. Also, as has been pointed out earlier, the ballad attributes Haru Singh's success in the land of the Bhot to the invisible protection he receives from the spirits of his ancestors, the *pitras*, to whom he prays before he starts on his mission. By way of a reasonable conclusion, thus, it can be safely said that the tale of Haru Singh Heet, as told in the ballad this paper has studied, is a legend with myths or mythic elements braided into it; and it is also a legend that qualifies as a chapter in the oral history of Kumaun.

Works Cited

(All references to the text of the ballad, which can also be called a heroic poem, are from the book titled 'Veer Balak Haru Singh Heet' (वीर बालक हरू सिंह हीत) in Kumauni dialect and in Devnagari script, authored by Kheemanand Sharma and published by Kumauni Sahitya Sadan, Delhi, in 1975. Every quote from the text, in indent and followed by the page number/s in parentheses, is in English transliteration by the author of this paper who, having been born and having lived in Kumaun in his early years, is sufficiently familiar and conversant with Kumauni dialect)

Armstrong, Karen. *A Short History of Myth*. Canongate Books, 2005.

Cox, Marian Roalfe. *An Introduction to Folk-Lore*. London: David Nutt, 1895.

Dundes, Alan. *The Study of Folklore*. Prentice Hall, 1965.

Grim, Jacob. *The German Legends of the Brothers Grim, vol. I*. Translated and edited by Donald Ward. Philadelphia: Institute for the Study of Human Issues (ISHI), 1981. (The original, *Deutsche Sagen*, was published in two volumes in the years 1816 and 1818).

Hansen, Kathryn. *Grounds for Play: The Nautanki Theatre of North India*. University of California Press, 1992.

Regmi, Mahesh C. *Imperial Gorkha: An Account of Gorkhali Rule in Kumaun (1791-1815)*. Adroit Publishers, 1999.

Sims, Martha C. and Martine Stephens. *Living Folklore: An Introduction to the Study of People and Their Traditions*. Utah State University Press, 2011.

Tangherlini, T. R. "'It Happened Not Too Far From Here...': A Survey of Legend Theory and Characterization". *Western Folklore*, vol.49, No. 4 (Oct 1990). pp 371-390.

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